

**ASSESSMENT OF HEALTH LIFE STYLE ADHERENCE OF WOMEN LIVING IN URBAN AREAS
IN UZBEKISTAN****Akhmedova D.,***Assistant of the Department of Rehabilitation, Folk medicine and Physical Education, Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan***Usmankhodjaeva A.,***Associate professor, Head of the Department of Rehabilitation, Folk medicine and Physical Education, Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan***Sharipov U.***Assistant of the Department of Rehabilitation, Folk medicine and Physical Education, Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7495009>**Abstract.**

In January 2021, in order to assess the level of healthy living of the women of Uzbekistan, i.e. the observance of a healthy lifestyle, to identify many common diseases and problems among women, we conducted mass medical examinations (anthropometric examinations) among women in Namangan and Andijan cities. 276 women (aged 46-74 years) took part in the medical examination. We have studied all 276 women with age, gender, hereditary diseases, concomitant diseases, and have analyzed and evaluated them based on several principles. We put the data obtained into tables and diagrams so that it is easy to analyze. From the information obtained to us it became clear that anemia, heart stroke, diabetes are more common diseases and mortality, that is, 38% are observed in middle (105 units) – aged women, 34% in elderly (94 units) - old women.

Keywords: womens, nutrition, personal and public hygiene, bad habits.

Relevance: the concept of "Health" is interrelated with the concept of "lifestyle", which consists in the sum of certain socio-economic conditions as a stable way of life of representatives of a certain developed society. One of the important components of a healthy lifestyle is the moral values of the individual. Its components include daily labor, rest, sleep, proper nutrition, getting rid of bad habits and tempering. In the life of each person there will be a certain rhythm of life. In it, a certain amount of time is allocated for work, rest, nutrition, sleep. The rationality of the agenda is an integral part of a healthy lifestyle. In this, there are no strict rules, but the correct organization of the day will help the rational functioning of the organism. Correctly organized and practiced agenda increases the body's useful working coefficient, creates optimal conditions for rest and labor activity, prevents diseases, increases labor potential. [13] Properly organized labor activity is also a part of a healthy lifestyle. It is proved that physical and mental labor activity is organized systematically, normally, positively affects the nervous, cardiac vascular, muscle, bone, system. [16] As an etiopathogenic factor in the development of osteoarthritis, in combination with human hypodynamia, it is possible to cause insufficient intake of microelements in the composition of nutrition. Another of the main components of a healthy lifestyle, this is proper nutrition. Since the energy spent with the received food is always in balance, it is better to ensure that the daily diet contains enough protein, carbohydrates, fat. For the full functioning of the nervous system, a good sleep is necessary. It is necessary for the organism to restore itself, to ensure that the organs work well, sleep is qualitative and lasting. [15] Another important component is the proper organization of breathing, carrying out various

breathing exercises, saturating the body with oxygen this is also the main norm. One important component of ya'na is the proper organization of breathing, carrying out various breathing exercises, saturating the body with oxygen this is also the main norm. To lead a healthy lifestyle, it is necessary to give up bad habits. Smoking, drinking are the very first culprits of this health.

The optimal physical mode of movement is the most important component of a healthy lifestyle. It is based on systematic physical exertion and sports training. To prevent diseases, to cope with it, we must increase the endurance of the organism, the protective force. We can achieve this only with physical activity and sports. [14] We have also developed and implemented several decrees and decisions aimed at healthy lifestyle in Uzbekistan.

In particular, work is being carried out based on decrees of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev dated October 30, 2020 № 6110 "On wide promotion of healthy lifestyle and development of mass sports". [1] In order to bring healthy children into the world, first of all parents and, of course, the family must be healthy. Healthy mother - bears healthy children. Therefore, trust in women's health is paid to special attention, but we are witnessing a meeting of chronic diseases among women. On the basis of promoting a healthy lifestyle among women, it is worthwhile to take into account the immaturity of the role of a woman in promoting the upbringing of children in the family. A healthy person lives a long and happy life. In the strengthening of women's health, it is important that a man have a positive attitude to his own health. [2] Our youth, including pupils, students and their knowledge of health, healthy lifestyle, practical qualifications and skills, and to what extent effective

and correct adherence to them will determine our nation, our people's level of advancement in the future, which is considered as the leading and decisive force of our society today, both in terms of number and activity, as the foundation of our future. A healthy lifestyle includes the sum of a person's aspirations for life, the sum of his actions aimed at strengthening health and preventing its deterioration. Hence, a healthy lifestyle is the activity of people aimed at maintaining and improving their health.[4] Currently, in Europe and North America, three-quarters of the mortality rate is attributed to cardiovascular, tumor, respiratory diseases and liver cirrhosis. [5] Given the aging trend of the population, it is possible to predict an increase in the proportion of these diseases in the structure of death in the future. This group plays an important role in the formation of diseases-the living environment and lifestyle, risk factors. [6] It is no secret to anyone now that the only way to maintain and strengthen human health, while remaining, longevity, is a healthy lifestyle. [7].

A number of measures are being taken in order to ensure the emergence of a strong immune system against the disease in every citizen, to abandon harmful habits, to follow the principles of proper nutrition, to organize systematic and effective rehabilitation and mass physical activity activities, to create appropriate infrastructure and other necessary conditions in this regard by regularly engaging in physical education [8] Including: Among women, there is an increase in diseases

of the cardiovascular, endocrine system, tumors. Undoubtedly, compliance with a healthy lifestyle is important in our prevention of these diseases, in the Prevention of further complications in the recovery of the health of those with the disease.

The purpose of the study: to form the concept of a healthy lifestyle among women of Uzbekistan, to promote its components, to identify negative factors that affect it, to communicate to the population, to identify the problems arising because of non-compliance with a healthy lifestyle, to find solutions to it, to study and analyze diseases. To identify the causes of death, find out the aspects associated with non-compliance with a healthy lifestyle and help to eliminate them.

Research methods and materials: we conducted a mass medical examination among 276 women in Namangan and Andijan cities. We conducted anthropometry among women, a special questionnaire (EQ-5D™) and a series of survey studies, sorted, evaluated and analyzed the data obtained.

Obtained results:

Mass medical examination was conducted in Namangan and Andijan cities, in total 276 women older than 25 years passed medical examination. We divided them into groups by age. In the distribution of who by age, 25-44 young people were 44, 45-60 years old, middle-aged 105, 61-75 years old, 94, 76-90 years old, elderly 33.

We put these indicators on the diagram. (1 picture)

From our diagram it can be seen that most of the women studied are of middle and old age. This age is exactly the age of Labor. It is among the contingent that the introduction of a healthy lifestyle can eliminate the problems that may arise in the future.

We divides women by diseases (2 figure)

Hypertension, obesity, anemia, ischemic heart diseases, cholecystitis, diabetes, malnutrition, do not eat foods rich in vitamins, informality of sleep can cause many of these diseases.

We studied women in terms of diseases that can be encountered in women. (Figure 3)

As can be seen from this diagram, among the Andijan and Namangan women, there has been a lot of women-specific inflammation, which can be due to the fact that they did not undergo timely medical examinations or that the medical deposit was not well scratched. We distributed the EQ-5D™ questionnaire to women during the examination, through which we aimed to evaluate the quality of life. The questions in this questionnaire cover adherence to a healthy life-

style, harmful habits, attitude to physical activity, understanding of healthy eating, understanding of medical culture among the ordinary population.

For example: Have you followed diet? The 72% of patients who received the following result on the question, 38% of patients responded «there was no opportunity to follow up on my case», as patients tried to follow up. What is more dependent on human health: heredity-12%, doctors-8%, Environment-10%, the person himself and his lifestyle-70%, do you feel like an absolute healthy person? Yes-75%, No-18%, -75%, it

is difficult to answer 7%. Do you do every day exercises? You will be touched by sports). Yes 65%, No, 30%, it is difficult to answer, 5% was answer of women. Do you think you have enough information about health and how to maintain and strengthen it? when they say that 70% of women say that yes, 25% no, 5% of women say that it is difficult to answer. In what form do you want to get information about health? When asked, in the form of lectures, 60%, in the form of games, 30%, in the form of events (expositions, festivities, etc.), 10% came out. The best nutrition diet that you think: announced by well-known people, 10% said, 25% of those who received a questionnaire on a good website on the internet, helped your friends, 35%, appointed by a doctor, 30%, regularly engaged in physical education and mass sports, as well as ensuring the appearance of a strong immune system against the disease in each citizen by forming vital, a number of measures are being taken in order to organize restoration and rehabilitation works and mass physical activity activities systematically and efficiently, to create appropriate infrastructure and other necessary conditions in this regard

DISCUSSION

When foreign data are examined, the highest indicators of morbidity and mortality among women fall on women older than 65 years.

And in Uzbekistan, based on the data obtained and the diagram, we can say that in Namangan and Andijan, when all 276 women were examined, the incidence of obesity, whiplash, ischemic heart disease was exactly the same as in middle and old age. Ensuring that every citizen develops a strong immune system against the disease through regular physical activity and mass sports and the formation of life skills for a healthy lifestyle, the elimination of harmful habits, adherence to the principles of proper nutrition, rehabilitation and rehabilitation and systematic physical activity and effective organization, a number of measures are being taken to create the appropriate infrastructure and other necessary conditions in this regard.

CONCLUSION:

1. An unhealthy lifestyle, an irrational diet can lead to high rates
2. Low level of medical culture among women and indifference to one's own health can also be reason.
3. We must ensure that medical professionals form a medical culture among women, that health is an invaluable wealth given to man.
4. Sluggish activity (low activity) leads to an increase in body weight, an increase in the amount of cholesterol in the blood and, as a result, the development of non-infectious diseases.

5. Among women there is an increase in diseases of the cardiovascular, endocrine system, tumors. Undoubtedly, compliance with a healthy lifestyle is important in our prevention of these diseases, in the Prevention of further complications in the recovery of the health of those with the disease.

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